

Appendix 4: Data collected on infructescence of *A. triandra* in the study plots in Meethirigala Forest Reserve (MFR 1, 2, and 3) and Yagirala Forest Reserve (YFR 1, 2, and 3)

Plot number	Average no. of fruits per infructescence	Average number of stems containing infructescence per clump	Average number of fruits per clump	Number of clumps with infructescence per plot	Number of <i>A. triandra</i> fruits per clump	Percentage of <i>A. triandra</i> infructescence per plot
Meethirigala Forest Reserve						
MFR 1	170	2	340	10	3400	31%
MFR 2	140	3	420	9	3780	30%
MFR 3	220	2	440	18	7920	64%
Yagirala Forest Reserve						
YFR 1	185	2	370	15	5550	52%
YFR 2	250	1	250	6	1500	30%
YFR 3	190	3	400	12	4800	48%
Average	193	2	370	12	4440	43%